

IOT BASED VEHICLE TRACKING SAFETY MONITORING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The current generation sometimes needs the data. Every day, more and more people rely on technology. We have thus devised the novel concept of "Vehicle safety System utilizing RFID and GPS" to merge the capabilities of modern technology with the need for data transfer. We describe a proposal to monitor a car using GPS and IoT in order to address the shortcomings of traditional paper-based solutions. In addition to monitoring Cabs/Taxis, stolen cars, school/college buses, etc., this Vehicle Tracking System may be utilized for Accident Detection Alert Systems, Soldier Tracking Systems, and many more with just minor hardware and software modifications.

Keywords: Sensors, Lcd Display, Gps, Rfid, Wi-Fi, Iot, Buzzer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tracing and detecting car theft has grown more important in recent years. Maintaining the vehicle's security is a top priority. While numerous mechanisms already exist, they are often inefficient and expensive. Thus, an effective security system is required. It is the goal of this research to identify instances of car theft. The node MCU is the central component of a GPS system. The vehicle's location was determined with the use of GPS and a Wi-Fi module (ESP 8266). The Global Positioning System (GPS) can pinpoint the position of the stolen gadget no matter the weather. With the help of a GPS antenna and Internet of Things, it provides the device's coordinates. Its purpose is to notify the owner of the vehicle's location using its precise latitude and longitude coordinates. A single switch activates the whole system whenever a car is parked outside. The preceding steps are repeated if a car theft has occurred, and the relevant details are shared through the internet of things (IOT). An anti-theft and tracking system for vehicles is installed in the client's car to deter and locate potential car thieves.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Survey: Real-time Precise Point Positioning: Differential GPS Based on IGS Ultra Rapid Product, SICE Annual Conference

In this study, we go into the issue of single-frequency GPS precise point placement (PPP). Using the P code signal, which is only available to authorized persons, or using dual-frequency, which is often done in a post-processing method, is the only way to accomplish GPS PPP in the past. Hence, a PPP service that is available to the public in real-time remains an issue. In this study, we provide a differential GPS method with the potential to deliver near-PPP service in real time. The suggested approach is capable of delivering wide-area DGPS service because it uses the IGS ultra-rapid product to generate vector differential GPS correction. We demonstrate that a standard GPS receiver can also make use of the correction by translating the vector into a scalar form, resulting in an accurate point placement in real time.

Experimentally Evaluation of GPS/GSM Based System Design

In order to experimentally test the developed system, this study set out to create a hardware and software of the GPS built around the GSM network. The control station and the mobile unit make up the two halves of the projected GPS/GSM based system paradigm. The mobile unit is a personal computer (PC-A) with a GSM modem (A) and GPS receiver (B) attached via USB; the control station seems to be another PC (PC-B) with a GSM modem (B). With this set up, SMS protocol is accessible to exchange data between PC-A and PC-B. Accuracy of less than 9 meters when using standard GPS and 0.6 meters when using differential GPS has been achieved after successful implementation and testing of the system's operations, interfaces, connections, network capacity, and reception in between mobile unit and indeed the control station.

Design and implementation of remote monitoring system based on gsm

An SMS of GSM-based remote monitoring system is introduced as wireless monitoring systems find increasing demand. The system's hardware and software are developed after the overall design has been completed. The remote signal in this system is sent over the GSM network. The central monitoring station and the outpost both play an important role in the system as a whole. A computer and a GSM communication module (TC35) form the heart of the monitoring center. The RS232 cable links the PC to the TC35. A GSM TC35 communication module, an MSP430F149 MCU, a display, sensors, and a data aggregation and processing unit are all part of the remote monitoring station. VB is used to create the software that runs the control room and the outposts. The demonstration results reveal that the system is capable of monitoring and controlling the transmission between the monitoring center and the distant monitoring station, thereby realizing the remote oversight functions.

Existing system:

Series of signals, alarms, and biometric systems are the most common types of systems. But, the market is flooded with expensive options. Using the car's buzzer is a simple way to deter theft. It may not be helpful to use a buzzer or alarm detecting while your automobile is far away from you. Several sensors, including pressure, tilt, shock, and door sensors, are included into automobile alarm systems to deter vehicle theft. There are, however, drawbacks to these systems, such as their expensive price tag, high false-alarm rate, and ease of disablement. Recent developments in computational hardware and software have allowed the automotive industry to create cheap automated biometrics-based identification and verification systems, which should help with these issues. Individuals may be identified and verified via the use of a variety of biometrics, such as facial detection, facial traits, hand geometry, handwriting, and voice. You can always change your login information if somebody learns it, but there's no way to modify your iris, retina, or fingerprint. On the other hand, biometric has its own disadvantages, such as the systems not being 100% accurate, requiring integration and/or additional hardware, and being unable to be reset once compromised. If someone gets a functional duplicate of these, you have little options for security beyond using passwords or a different finger. Protection against theft via alarm has its limitations, including the fact that it may be disarmed during an attempted theft, that most automobiles have similar noises, and that the alarm's volume can be reduced in congested locations.

Proposed system:

This study details a method that uses the Internet of Things to identify stolen vehicles. Although there are a number of systems now in use for this purpose, the suggested solution addresses the main drawbacks of the alternatives. As the dc motor begins, signaling the theft of a car, Arduino activates the GPS and IOT, sending a message of alarm to the vehicle's owner while also posting the vehicle's current location online through the internet of things and a Wi-Fi module. For the sake of simplicity, the whole system may be controlled by a single toggle. Planned setup.

III. METHODOLOGY

Vehicle tracking involves keeping tabs on the vehicle's whereabouts in the form of coordinates (longitude and latitude) (GPS coordinates). Location is quantified by its Geolocation. The technology is ideal for use in the great outdoors. Taxis, stolen cars, school buses, and other types of transportation all benefit from our Vehicle Tracking System Project. The intended use of this circuit is to monitor a moving vehicle's position. In general, tracking devices are Produce by use of GPS. The solution is easy and inexpensive. Often, fleet managers will utilize a tracking system to keep tabs on where their vehicles are and where they've been. This is a fantastic strategy for protecting our automobiles against theft. We get GPS coordinates from this system, which we then use to pinpoint the location of our car on online maps. These tagging technologies allow for the instantaneous exchange of transportation-related data. In addition, riders may get up-to-the-minute updates on where their bus, taxi, or cab is. This means that passengers will be able to track the exact location and arrival time of their bus, taxi, or cab through their mobile devices.

Block diagram:

Figure 1: Functional block diagram

GPS

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a satellite based navigation system that provides location and time information. The system is freely accessible to anyone with a GPS receiver and unobstructed line of sight to at least four of GPS satellites. A GPS receiver calculates its position by precisely timing the signals sent by GPS satellites. GPS is nowadays widely used and also has become an integral part of smart phones

Figure 2: GPS module

RFID:

Module for RFID Reader (EM-18) It employs radio frequency waves to select and classify various items. An RFID tag is used, and information is sent directly and instantly between the two devices. Vcc, gnd, LED/buzz, data0, data1, Transmitter (Tx), and a select pin are all present (sel). The device's UART protocol enables direct connection between the transmitter and receiver pins of a microcontroller. The RFID reader module is equipped with an RF signal transmitter for start and completion to the tag and a receiver/signal detector for picking up signals broadcast by the tag. High-frequency magnetic field waves are generated by a Radio Frequency (RF) module and also an antenna in a Reader.

Figure 3: RFID module

LCD Connections:

Depending on how many lines are used for connection to the microcontroller, there are 8-bit and 4-bit LCD modes. The appropriate mode is determined at the beginning of the process in a phase called "initialization". In the first case, the data are transferred through outputs D0-D7 as it has been already explained. In case of 4-bit LCD mode, for the sake of saving valuable I/O pins of the microcontroller, there are only 4 higher bits (D4-D7) used for communication, while other may be left unconnected.

Figure 4: LCD display module

Consequently, each data is sent to LCD in two steps: four higher bits are sent first (that normally would be sent through lines D4-D7), four lower bits are sent afterwards. With the help of initialization, LCD will correctly connect and interpret each data received. Besides, with regards to the fact that data are rarely read from LCD (data mainly are transferred from microcontroller to LCD) one more I/O pin may be saved by simple connecting R/W pin to the Ground. Such saving has its price. Even though message displaying will be normally performed, it will not be possible to read from busy flag since it is not possible to read from display.

IV. RESULT

Figure 5: Monitoring result

V. CONCLUSION

The "tracing down the car using IOT and GPS" project is a prototype for a GPS- and Internet-enabled vehicle-tracking gadget. The use of a Vehicle Tracking System led to greater efficiency and enhanced fleet management, which in turn increased ROI. You may do more work in a given time frame if you manage your schedule and travel routes more efficiently. Automobile tracking, whether for personal or commercial use, boosts security,

communication, performance monitoring, and output. As a result, it will become more important to our daily lives in the future year.

VI. REFERENCES

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